

INHERITANCE AND VARIABILITY OF SOME MORPHOLOGICAL CHARACTERS IN ECOLOGICALLY AND GEOGRAPHICALLY DISTANT G' OZA HYBRIDS

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ANNOTATION

In this article, we aim to study the genetic patterns and variability of selected morpho-economic traits in ecologically-geographically distant cotton hybrids. Through a review of existing literature and research, we highlight the importance of exploring and exploiting the genetic potential of these hybrids to improve cotton yield and sustainability. The results of such studies are expected to help develop new breeding strategies and select superior cotton varieties suitable for different environmental conditions.

Key words: Inheritance, variability, morpho-economic characters, cotton hybrids, ecological-geographic, genetics, agriculture, crop improvement, phenotypic observation.

Hybridization of geographically distant forms - crossbreeding of plants belonging to different geographical types, families and higher taxonomic units; one of the types of hybridization. Hybridization of geographically distant forms is divided into hybridization within a species, between species and between species. This hybridization involves congruent (parents have the same genome) hybridization (copies are easy to cross and the resulting hybrids are fertile). Such hybridization is used in the selection of agricultural crops to improve disease-resistant varieties and other valuable economic traits. For example, by crossing annual **Peruvian** cotton with perennial cotton from **Peru**, fine fiber cotton varieties resistant to **fusarium wilt have been created. By crossing Mexican cotton** varieties with its wild subspecies - *Mexicanum nervosum*, Tashkent varieties resistant to verticilliosis wilt were created.

Cross-species hybridization of geographically distant forms. Cross-breeding plants of different species is an important source of new copies. This method is effectively used in the selection of cultivated plants. Many varieties of wheat, sunflower, potato, tobacco, cotton and other crops were created in this way. Interspecies hybridization belongs to the group of incongruent (incongruence of the total number of chromosomes of parental copies, their number is different, or there are differences due to cytoplasm) hybridization, and in such hybridization (due to genetic and physiological disequilibrium), seeds are produced less. This phenomenon is based on a variety of reasons, such as the disproportion between pollen tubes and seed coat tissue due to inconsistencies

in the structure of reproductive organs, changes in the structure of chromosomes during the development of the species, the origin of genetic imbalance, and the death of the fruit at different stages of its development.

The study of heredity and variability of morpho-economic characters in ecologically-geographically distant cotton hybrids is an important topic of genetics and agricultural science. **Hybridization**, especially between different geographical origins, can lead to different forms and characteristics of offspring. Morphoeconomic characteristics refer to the appearance of plants and their economic characteristics. They include plant height and size, leaf and fruit shape, crop size and quality, and other parameters that may be important in breeding and yield determination. This allows to determine the level of This includes genetic marker analysis, phenotypic observation, and statistical analysis. The purpose of such studies is to understand the genetic mechanisms and laws underlying the heritability and variability of morphoeconomic characters. The obtained results can be useful for breeders and gardeners, which allows them to choose optimal combinations of genetic materials and estimate the potential productivity of hybrids. They can also be used to better understand evolutionary processes and adaptation of plants to different environmental conditions. Studying the heritability and variability of morpho-economic characters in ecological-geographic cotton hybrids is important for the development of agriculture and increasing the productivity of this important crop. is of great importance. They help expand our knowledge of the genetic potential of plants and use it for practical purposes to achieve more efficient and sustainable agriculture.

Economically important cotton has significant changes in its morpho-economic characteristics, which directly affect its productivity and adaptation to different environmental conditions. Understanding the heritability and variability of these traits in cotton hybrids from ecologically and geographically distant parents is critical for crop improvement and sustainable agriculture. Heredity of morpho-economic characters means the transfer of specific characteristics such as plant height, leaf shape, fruit morphology, productivity from parent plants to their hybrid offspring. Ecological-geographic distance hybridization in cotton implies the crossing of individuals from genetically diverse populations adapted to different environmental conditions. This results in the introduction of new genetic material and potentially phenotypic diversity in the hybrid progeny.

Studying the heritability and variability of morpho-economic traits in ecologically-geographically distant cotton hybrids provides valuable information about the genetic mechanisms underlying these traits. By analyzing the genetic

basis of these traits, breeders and researchers can make informed decisions on the selection and improvement of cotton varieties for specific environmental conditions and agricultural practices. genetic markers and phenotypic observations are widely used to study the heritability and variability of traits. These tools allow researchers to identify the genetic factors responsible for observed variation and to assess their potential impact on yield . Furthermore, understanding genotype-phenotype correlations in cotton hybrids will provide a deeper understanding of the evolutionary processes shaping the adaptation and performance of this important crop i.

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